

THE ROLE OF LOCAL RAW MATERIALS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DRY LUBRICANT COMPOSITES

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In recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out in our country aimed at developing the chemical industry and making effective use of local raw materials and mineral resources. At the same time, practical measures are being taken to rapidly develop and diversify the chemical industry, with a particular focus on the rational use of domestic raw materials.

According to scientists, by 2026 the national economy will require nearly 6 million tonnes of metal. Moreover, the complex situation in the global economy and disruptions in logistics chains are creating difficulties for large metallurgical enterprises. During his visit to Bekobod, the head of our state, after becoming acquainted with the activities of a major metallurgical enterprise there, particularly stressed that under today's difficult conditions, the goal can only be achieved by rapidly developing our own metallurgical industry.

It should be noted that one of the key factors in further developing the metallurgical industry is the production of inexpensive and high-quality construction materials. In addition, shaping metals into various dimensions is of particular importance. Therefore, metal processing and production of different sizes require deeper study of the composition of steel wires and the mechanical effects occurring on their surfaces. For drawing and processing metals, dry lubricant composites are used. The development of a technology for producing dry lubricant composites from local raw materials is thus a pressing issue.

Throughout the years, various scholars, including H. E. Sliney, A. G. Kostornov, V. B. Niste, A. Abdulkhayev, A. Nodirov and others, have conducted research on producing dry lubricant composites for metal processing, and these studies are still ongoing.

Modern machinery and industry components wear out quickly under friction and high temperatures, limiting their long-term reliability. For this reason, it is of great importance to create dry lubricant composites capable of operating even without additional lubrication.

The technology of obtaining dry lubricant composites generally involves the following stages: preparing raw materials, mixing components in precise proportions, heating and forming a homogeneous mass, shaping into monoliths,

grinding, and finally packaging the finished product. The main task is to determine the optimal composition of the matrix and lubricant additives, while also controlling their micro- and macrostructure.

Scientific and technical sources show that today both dry and liquid composites are used for drawing steel wires and shaping them into different forms. Calcium stearate and sodium stearate salts are considered the main raw materials for steel wire drawing. In CIS countries, many different composite formulations have been proposed for obtaining dry lubricant composites.

At present, the dry lubricant composite used for drawing steel wires in our Republic is being imported from China and Russia. Certain scientific and practical results have already been achieved in developing a technology for producing this dry lubricant composite from local raw materials. In particular, the rapid development of the chemical industry in our country and the establishment of new production capacities are leading to an increase in both the variety and volume of competitive products. Among these achievements are the scientific and practical results obtained in developing a technology for producing the dry lubricant composite used in steel wire drawing on the basis of local raw materials.

However, shortcomings have been observed in optimising the amount of calcium and sodium stearate salts and in the sequence of mixing the supplementary materials.

Indeed, the use of local raw materials in the development of self-lubricating composite materials carries great scientific and practical significance. This can be seen in the figure below:

Figure 1

Natural minerals available in Uzbekistan — such as kaolin, graphite, bentonite, talc, limestone, and dolomite — serve as important components in the production of lubricant composites. Their physical-mechanical properties allow them to function within the material either as reinforcing or lubricating phases. This, in turn, creates environmental advantages. The use of local natural materials reduces dependence on external sources, lowers transportation costs, and decreases ecological burden. Powders produced from local raw materials are suitable for powder metallurgy, coating technologies, and sintering processes. Moreover, their chemical and phase compositions allow for the application of various synthesis methods. Research into the effective use of local raw materials generates new technological approaches, contributes to the development of a national scientific school, and lays the foundation for producing innovative products with wide industrial application.

Conclusion. Technologies developed using local raw materials (titanium oxide, ferrotitanium, feldspar, borax, graphite, mica, starch, and others) possess several advantages. Firstly, they substitute costly imported components and reduce production costs. Secondly, they enable the effective use of domestic mineral resources. Thirdly, they create opportunities to establish laboratory and industrial technologies adapted to local conditions.

Thus, developing a technology for producing dry lubricant composites based on local raw materials is of strategic significance not only for scientific progress, but also in terms of economic efficiency, import substitution, and environmental sustainability.

References:

1. Abdulkhayev A., “Establishing the production of dry lubricant composites based on local raw materials.” Monograph. Nam DU. 2023
2. Toshpulatova., L.M. “Socio-economic potential of the region.” - T .: TDIU, 2004. - 123 p.
3. Turamuratov I.B., “Integration of science and practice as a mechanism of effective geological development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” .Mat-ly. mejdunar. nauch.- techn. konf. 2014. S. 7-9.
4. Dunyashin N.S. Abstract, Tashkent, 2019.
5. Abstract. Technology of preparation of electrode coatings using local raw materials to improve the characteristics of welds. News of the National University of Uzbekistan, 2019.

